

Research Data Management for Arts and Humanities: Integrating Voices of the Community

The Brand-new, Collective Publication of the DARIAH Working Group on Research Data Management

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Summary. The poster showcases the publication “Research Data Management for Arts and Humanities: Integrating Voices of the Community” issued in 2023 by the DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Humanities and Arts) Working Group on Research Data Management. The collective, open-access volume brings together case studies and consolidated experiences with a strong pan-European approach.

A frequently voiced concern about the Open Science paradigm is that it has not had the same impact on the different disciplines. Research areas and researchers who are heavily dependent on third-party data are still facing complex legal, ethical, technical, infrastructural and interoperability challenges and their needs form a rather underrepresented blind spot in the open research culture. A particular Open Science challenge in research data workflows in the Arts and Humanities domain is their dependence on cultural heritage sources hosted and curated in museums, libraries, galleries and archives. The availability of digital (digitised and born-digital) Cultural Heritage Data is fundamental to research in many disciplines in the Arts and Humanities. Still, Cultural Heritage collections are usually not made available digitally with research/academic reuse in mind. A major difficulty when scholars interact with heritage data is that Cultural Heritage institutions, universities and other research-performing organisations are embedded into very different legal, funding, structural and organisational frameworks.

DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Humanities and Arts) is a permanent research infrastructure financed by the European Union which supports digitally-powered research and teaching across the Arts and Humanities (see: <https://www.dariah.eu/about/dariah-in-nutshell/>). It includes institutions and national networks in the whole European continent and beyond. In DARIAH, several working groups are active. The Working Group Research Data Management (see: <https://www.dariah.eu/activities/working-groups/research-data-management/>) is composed of volunteering members who are Research Data Management professionals or scholars. Members who have so far

taken part in the working group's activities with continuity are active in the following countries: Belgium, Germany, The Netherlands, Poland, Switzerland.

The working group organised a hybrid (both on-premise and remote) writing session in June 2022 in Warsaw (Poland) with the aim of describing aforementioned challenges, interactions, along with a variety of situations and approaches. The outcome is the publication "Research Data Management for Arts and Humanities: Integrating Voices of the Community".

It brings together case studies and consolidated experiences from the members of the group about:

- How certain Arts and Humanities and Cultural Heritage institutions developed capacities for data support;
- Ways in which Cultural Heritage professionals can be efficiently involved in open and sustainable Arts and Humanities data workflows;
- How to facilitate the reuse, dissemination and solidification of researcher-friendly, FAIR-by-design curation practices of arts and humanities research data, including also sensitive data;
- How multilingualism can be supported throughout this work;
- How to solve the problem of long-term digital preservation.

Furthermore, the publication outlines, with a comparative approach, research data management policies issued by the European Union as well as by some European countries (Belgium, France, Germany and Poland), including information on very recent developments in France and Germany.

The publication is available both as a dynamic GitLab project (<https://gitlabce.rrz.uni-hamburg.de/uahh-digitaledienste/rdm-for-arts-and-humanities>) and as a static PDF (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8059626](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8059626)). It will be soon published in the online book series [DARIAH-DE Working Papers](#).

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